

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EFFECTIVENESS OF IMPROVING THE HYGIENIC PROPERTIES OF REMOVABLE PARTIAL DENTURES IN PATIENTS WITH PARTIAL TOOTH LOSS AND PATHOLOGY

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Abstract

The ability of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms to penetrate from the mucosal defects of the oral cavity, the surface of dental prostheses, and prosthetic tissue beds into the bloodstream is extremely dangerous for the body. The method of assessing the colonization of conditionally pathogenic microflora in vitro using alloy samples for the manufacture of removable partial dentures allows for an objective evaluation of the level of bacterial contamination of dental materials and prediction of the effectiveness of hygiene measures for removable dentures, which is particularly important for patients with periodontal inflammatory diseases. The structural heterogeneity, low surface cleanliness, and poor polishability of cobalt-chromium alloys promote the adhesion of microbial cells, thus increasing the colonization of microflora on the material's surface. Gold-based alloy samples, as well as cobalt-chromium alloys with electroplating, showed identical results of reduced microorganism sorption and good hygienic properties.

Keywords: periodontal diseases; removable partial dentures; hygienic properties.

Oral Cavity Microflora is represented by aerobic, anaerobic, and facultatively anaerobic microorganisms, with concentrations of 10^7 – 10^8 colony-forming units (CFU) per 1 ml of saliva. The ability of conditionally pathogenic microflora to penetrate from mucosal defects in the oral cavity, the surface of dental prostheses, and prosthetic tissue beds into the bloodstream is extremely dangerous for the body. Non-compliant dental prostheses contribute to the persistence of microorganisms, which is especially problematic for patients with partial tooth loss and periodontal pathology. Under the influence of toxins, the tissue structures of the prosthetic bed lose their resistance to mechanical stress. This leads to the formation of chronic infection foci, followed by sensitization and a high risk of developing systemic autoimmune diseases. The insufficient immune response, combined with prolonged colonization by conditionally pathogenic microflora causing damage to oral tissues, leads to severe pathological processes in periodontal tissues, resulting in premature tooth loss.

Improving the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment through the stability of long-term clinical outcomes is possible only with the preservation of the sustained quality indicators of dental restorations over time. This is not achievable without a reasoned choice of structural material, especially when periodontal diseases are present. A comparative analysis of data regarding the species composition and degree of bacterial contamination by conditionally patho-

genic microflora of the structural materials for removable partial dentures will not only identify the material least susceptible to colonization but also determine the factors that govern the adhesion of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms.

Objective of the study – to study the hygienic properties of materials for making partial dentures in patients with partial tooth loss and periodontal pathology by evaluating the colonization of dental alloy samples by conditionally pathogenic microflora in an in vitro experiment.

Material and Methods

The experiment used bacterial cultures covering a wide range of conditionally pathogenic microflora representatives: *Staphylococcus aureus* wood 95, *Escherichia coli* B, *Streptococcus pyogenes* 5, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 573, *Candida albicans*. The selection of these bacteria strains was based on the results of our own studies and literary sources.

The essence of the method was the comparative evaluation of the survival of microorganisms from five clinically significant species (*S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. pyogenes*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*) on the surface of samples made of cobalt-chromium alloy for removable dentures “Gialloy PA Co/Cr” (BK Giuliani Chemie, Germany), gold alloy (“KASDENT-B,” ZAO “Stilident,” Russia), and cobalt-chromium alloy with a gold coating “KEMADENT” from the Russian enterprise AO “Supermetall,” applied by electroplating.

Wax reproductions, $20 \times 20 \times 0.5$ mm in size, were modeled on a refractory model and cast from the appropriate materials in a dental laboratory. The samples were polished. Ten samples were made and examined for each material, a total of 30 samples.

0.2 ml of a microorganism mixture (suspension) was applied to each side of the sample. The initial concentration of microorganisms was $4 \times 10^5 - 5 \times 10^5$ CFU/ml. The suspension was evenly distributed across the surface of the samples with a sterile spatula. Contaminated test samples were placed in sterile Petri dishes for 1 to 10 days, and the Petri dishes were then placed in a microclimate chamber where optimal parameters for microbial growth were maintained (90–99% humidity at 37°C).

The quantitative content of microorganisms on the material samples was evaluated on the 2nd, 7th, and 10th days of the experiment. After the specified periods, the samples were shaken twice in 5 ml of sterile saline. The first shaking was considered to be a hygienic cleaning procedure for the dentures by the patients. Cultures were then performed after the second shaking on various nutrient media according to standard methods. The cultures were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, and at 25–30°C for 48 hours when growing fungi.

After the necessary experimental periods, the colonies were counted per 1 cm² of the nutrient medium.

Results and Discussion

The obtained results of colonization of the samples by conditionally pathogenic microflora indicate that only the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* culture demonstrated the greatest growth on the tested materials until the end of the experiment. The most significant number of *P. aeruginosa* bacteria was recorded on the cobalt-chromium alloy sample on the 10th day of the study. The number of viable *P. aeruginosa* bacteria, compared to the initial colonization, increased by more than 19.8% and amounted to 4.1×10^3 CFU/cm². On other samples, the increase in *P. aeruginosa* bacteria was less pronounced. For example, for the gold-based alloy sample, the number of viable *P. aeruginosa* bacteria increased by 17.8% and amounted to 3×10^3 CFU/cm² on the 10th day, while the alloy with electroplating showed an increase of 14.6%, amounting to 2.1×10^3 CFU/cm².

Staphylococcus aureus, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Candida albicans* also retained their viability and ability to multiply on all studied samples until the 10th day of the experiment, but the growth of CFU was less intense compared to *P. aeruginosa*. The maximum number of CFU for the microorganisms listed above, which increased by the end of the study period, was recorded on the cobalt-chromium alloy sample.

On the cobalt-chromium alloy sample, on the 10th day of the study, the number of viable *S. aureus* bacteria increased by 53.1% compared to the gold-based alloy sample, reaching 5.2×10^3 CFU/cm², and by 69% compared to the alloy with electroplating. For *E. coli* and *S. pyogenes* on the cobalt-chromium alloy sample, the number of viable bacteria on the 10th day increased by 41.8% and 14.8%, respectively, compared to the gold-based alloy colonization, reaching 1.01×10^3

CFU/cm² and 3.4×10^3 CFU/cm², and increased by 45.6% compared to the alloy with electroplating.

For *C. albicans* on the cobalt-chromium alloy sample, the number of viable bacteria on the 10th day increased by 62.5% compared to the gold-based alloy colonization, reaching 1.3×10^3 CFU/cm², and by 76.7% compared to the alloy with electroplating.

Conclusions

1. The presented method for assessing colonization by conditionally pathogenic microflora in an in vitro experiment using alloy samples for the manufacture of removable partial dentures allows for an objective evaluation of the level of bacterial contamination of dental materials and the prediction of the effectiveness of hygiene measures for removable dentures. This is especially important for patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases.

2. All the studied samples were susceptible to colonization by conditionally pathogenic microorganisms. The degree of colonization depends on the chemical composition, surface roughness, and type of bacterial cultures.

3. The structural heterogeneity, low surface cleanliness, and poor polishability of the cobalt-chromium alloy promote the adhesion of microbial cells, thereby increasing the colonization of microflora on the material's surface. The gold-based alloy sample and the cobalt-chromium alloy with electroplating showed identical results in reduced microorganism sorption, as well as good hygienic properties.

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